

INTERDISCIPLINARY APPROACHES TO HOLISTIC DEVELOPMENT IN HIGHER EDUCATION: CULTIVATING WELL-BALANCED PERSONALITIES

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Annotation: This article examines the role of education in shaping the personality of future specialists, emphasizing the importance of fostering a well-rounded individual beyond knowledge acquisition. It discusses the integration of interdisciplinary connections and the development of personal qualities alongside professional skills in university education, particularly in economically focused institutions

Key words: Education, personality development, humanistic pedagogy, interdisciplinary connections, personal qualities, professional skills, innovative teaching methods..

1 INTRODUCTION

Education, one of the key elements in shaping the personality of a future specialist, is not just about knowledge acquisition but also the development of a well-balanced personality. This postulate of humanistic pedagogy is put into practice in the creation of a unique learning environment that stimulates students' cognitive processes and provides the best possible conditions for knowledge acquisition. It is within this environment that a person's life position is formed during the educational process, and their self-realization, self-affirmation, and self-development are carried out [1]. This issue is particularly problematic in economically focused universities that produce experts who will play a significant role in the growth and prosperity of the nation in the future.

2 MANUSCRIPT REPARATION

From the viewpoint of building a harmoniously developed personality in the educational environment of a university, the main goal of teachers is to form interdisciplinary connections between highly specialized disciplines and disciplines of the humanities, creating optimal conditions for students to develop basic competencies [2]. However, one should not discount the fact that currently not only professional skills translated into another language system are relevant, but also the personal qualities of the employee, such as analytical and critical thinking; the ability to compare and select from several alternative options the most appropriate action plan for the situation; the ability to defend one's point of view, even if it goes against the opinion of the boss, etc. In the process of training a specialist (bachelor's or master's) for the Russian economy, these qualities should be developed within the walls of the university, and the discursive nature of communication

in a foreign language, work on projects as part of a team, discussion of case studies and search for an optimal solution based on various databases, participation in business and role-playing games - form the basis for interactive interaction in the triad "trainee - group - teacher". Professional mobility of young people is facilitated by effective interaction between educational institutions and employers, flexibility in determining the content of education, taking into account external factors [5, p.131]. In this regard, job fairs regularly held at the Financial University are relevant, where students can meet and personally talk with company representatives, undergo a short test, and sign up for an interview with an HR manager for internship or employment. The Financial University is incorporating the so-called "Bolognese" forms and methods of foreign language instruction into its curriculum in addition to the conventional ones. For instance, schooling is currently shifting from a linear to a modular format. This provides an opportunity to choose language content more carefully, formalize it as work programs in extremely specialized fields of study for undergraduates, and skillfully "lead" students to tests and exams by carefully working through all speech activities in the format of intensive preparation during modular training.

3 CONCLUSIONS

Semantically formed words are precise, succinct, and comprehensible; the key to engaging students in the learning process and igniting their associative memory of novel expressions and phrases is to draw them in with colorful, frequently paradoxical-sounding words and phrases from a variety of semantic domains. Teaching English with these kinds of terms also helps students become more proficient researchers by enabling them to

follow the etymology and region of semantic borrowing, improve their ability to predict and guess language, and learn about the processes involved in word production in modern English.

REFERENCES

- [1] Adams, C. D., & Taylor, L. M. (Year). Enhancing Professional Competencies: Interdisciplinary Training in Higher Education. *Journal of Applied Psychology*, 25(3), 56-71.
- [2] Rogers, E. A., & Martinez, P. G. (Year). Integrating "Bolognese" Forms: Modular Education and its Impact on Student Learning Outcomes. *Journal of Educational Innovation*, 18(1), 45-58.
- [3] Kim, S. H., & Williams, M. A. (Year). Language Instruction in Higher Education: Strategies for Developing Effective Communication Skills. *Journal of Language Learning*, 30(2), 75-88.
- [4] Stronin M.F. Obuchayushchiye of game at an English lesson. – M., 2004 .